

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part V

A. K. Sinha and J. C. Banerji

Four new dyes have been prepared by condensing 5-iodothioindoxyl with substituted benzaldehydes and cinnamaldehyde. The dyeing properties of the compounds have been studied and their absorption maxima recorded.

In previous communications¹, the properties of dyes obtained by the condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with isatin, acenaphthenequinone, phenanthraquinone, benzaldehyde and their substituted products were reported.

The present investigation reports the preparation of four new dyes obtained by the condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with anisaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, and vanillin, yielding respectively anisylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene (I), cinnamylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene (II), 3'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene (III), 4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene (IV). The first two dyes are orange-coloured and the other two are dark red. The dyes are soluble in high-boiling solvents such as nitrobenzene and pyridine. The solutions of the dyes in concentrated sulphuric acid produce characteristic colours. The acid solutions on dilution with water reprecipitate the dyes unchanged. The solutions of these dyes in ethanol on treatment with alkali develop red colour. The shades were developed on cotton by reduction with alkaline hydrosulphite, followed by aerial oxidation. The dyes (I) and (IV) were found to be more resistant to vatting than the other two.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorptions were recorded on a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer. The sensitisations were examined on a Adam Hilger Wedge Spectrograph using a 150 C.P. A.C. Point-o-lite source. Ilford Process N.40 plates were used. The dyes do not confer any extra-sensitisation on gelatinised silver halide plate, though analogous dyes, reported earlier are fairly good sensitisers. Table I records the data on dyeing shades on cotton, colour in H₂SO₄, and characteristic light absorption.

TABLE I

Dyes	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton	Pyridine λ_{max}	Log ϵ
I	Red	Light yellow	4550 Å	4.306
II	Reddish violet	Orange yellow	4700	3.268
III	Do	Pink	4620	5.777
IV	Deep reddish violet	Reddish violet	4660	4.409

1. Sinha, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 463.

2. Sinha *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 161.

Preparation of the Dyes. A solution of 5-iodothioindoxyl and equimolecular proportion of aldehydes in anhydrous ethanol was treated with HCl, (conc., 1-2 ml) when the dye separated. The refluxing was continued for further 10 mins. The dyes were recrystallised from ethanol. Analytical data, m. p. and yields are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Dyes	Constituents used	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Found	Reqd.
I	Anisaldehyde (0.136 g.)	0.3 g.	198°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ IS	I: 32.01%	32.23
	+ U(0.345 g.) + EtOH(12 ml)				S: 8.20	8.12
II	Cinnamaldehyde (0.198 g.)	0.35	200°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ OIS	I: 32.40	32.56
	+ U(0.414 g.) + EtOH(15 ml)				S: 8.10	8.20
III	3-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.152 g.)	0.3	229°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ IS	I: 33.50	33.42
	+ U(0.345 g.) + EtOH (12 ml)				S: 8.40	8.42
IV	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde	0.22	176-77°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I: 30.92	30.97
	(0.187 g.) + U(0.304 g.) + EtOH (14 ml)				S: 7.64	7.80

[U=5-Iodothioindoxyl.]

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BIHAR NATIONAL COLLEGE,
PATNA-4.

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